

FERULA L. SPECIES AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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A tribe of cypresses - Apiales. In most cases, it is a herbaceous plant, the leaves are arranged alternately, the leaves are leafless. The flower is bisexual, actinomorphic, located in an umbrella-shaped flower cluster, 4-5 members, the sepal is reduced in most cases, the corolla is free, not connected, the carpel is one, usually formed from two carpels, the node is bicameral, lower, seed endosperm. In the system of A. Takhtadjian (1987), 3 families are included in the tribe. The largest and most important of them are the Apiaceae and Araliaceae families.

The Araliaceae family is Araliaceae. The family belongs to more than 80 genera and includes 800 species. Most of the Aralia species grow in tropical and subtropical regions. Most of their species are found in the tropics of Malaysia, Indonesia and America. Aralia include small trees or shrubs and some creeping lianas. There are also perennial grass species. A band of leaves expands to form a branch and surrounds the stem. The leaves are placed alternately on the stem. A large, complex umbrella with balls. The flowers are relatively small, actinomorphic, bisexual, dioecious. Gulgorgani has two layers, 5 or 4 sepals, 5 stamens, and 5 or more stamens.

This family includes the medicinal plant Panax ginseng, Oplopanax, Aralia, Eleutherococcus and other ornamental plants.

Apiaceae family. This family includes more than 3000 species belonging to about 300 genera. They are widespread all over the world. According to the life

form, the family is dominated by annual and perennial grasses, and partly consists of semi-shrubs and shrubs. Arharo't (*Angelica ternata*), gulpar (*Heraclium*) and others can reach up to 3 meters in height. The leaves are divided to different levels, and there are whole ones. Most of the types (kovark) have a sheath (novi) at the base of the leaf. A simple or complex umbrella with a ball consists of a head. The color of the flowers is very diverse, the petals are complex, the petals are reduced to 5, small, the petals are 5, they are not budded. There are 5 seeds, 2 seeds, and the bottom of the knot. Flower formula: $Ca_5Co_5A_5G(2)$. The fruit is pistachio.

Representatives of the Zirados family can be found on almost all continents of the globe, but are more common in the subtropics. 422 species belonging to 97 genera of the family grow in Central Asia, 198 species belonging to 69 genera grow in Uzbekistan. The family is divided into 3 families. The largest of them, that is, the Apium family (*Apioideae*), which is rich in genera and species, includes the largest genera widespread in Uzbekistan and species with useful properties. Among them, 48 species of *Ferula*, 8 species of sedge (*Prangos*), 12 species of Cumin (*Bunium*), 12 species of *Elesticta* (*Elaeosticta*, *Scaligeria*) grow here.

Apart from these, parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), cumin (*Bunium persicum*), chives, dill (*Anethum graveolens*), carrots (*Daucus sativus*) are also considered as representatives of this family.

Representatives of the genus Kovrak - *Ferula* consist of perennial monocarpic (flowering and fruiting once in their life) and polycarpic (flowering and fruiting every year) stems with thick and tall grasses. The leaves are long-lobed, large, the leaves are divided several times, the sheaths of the leaves on the stem are well developed. The umbrellas are large and have many flowers. Flowers are unisexual or bisexual, yellow. Fruits are pistachios. Representatives of the category are mainly distributed in Eurasia and Africa. 48 species of it grow in

Uzbekistan. In Uzbekistan, the species known as *F. kuhistanica* - chayir, *F. karelinii* - itsigek, *F. sumbul* - sumbul, *F. foetida* - sassik kavrak are distributed in desert, hill and mountain regions (Fig. 3).

The carpets are distributed in the areas ranging from the desert to the upper parts of the mountains in saline, gypsum, small calcareous soils, gravelly and stony areas. One of the common species in the republic is *F. diversivittata*. Kokurak is a good fodder, honey-producing, medicinal and edible (korakv) plant.

Cumin - *Bunium* family includes perennial, nodular herbs. The ball leaves located at the throat of the root are long-banded and cut like a leaf. The flowers are 2 kinds of bisexual and unisex, and the petals are white. Many people know the type of cumin called fragrant cumin (*B. persicum*). It is a hairless perennial herb with a nodular, erect stem, flowing green color. It grows mainly in the southern districts of Uzbekistan on fine limestone soils, in the lower and middle parts of the mountain. Cumin blooms in June and ripens in July-August. This is a protected species that is used in the preparation of various dishes. It grows from seeds and buds.

Carrot (*Daucus*) (Fig. 2) is a thickened, fleshy tuber, the leaf is complexly claw-shaped, and its rod-shaped leaf band surrounds the stem. Cultivated carrot (*Daucus sativa*) with white flowers and thorny fruits is rich in vitamins A, C, B, B2 and is widely used in food. Cultivated varieties of carrots have been used in Central Asia for more than 2,000 years for cooking various dishes.

Black cumin (*Carum carvi*) (Fig. 1). It is used as a two-year, fragrant, aromatic, spice plant. The height is 40-60 cm, the stem branches in all directions, grows from the stem band, the leaves are 6-8 pairs, simple or double feather cut, the umbrella-shaped inflorescence has 20 flowers, the calyx, the petals are white or pink, the fruit is egg-shaped. It blooms and gives seeds in June-August.

The family includes edible carrot (*Daucus carota*), black cumin (*Sarum carvi*), common cumin (*Bunimum persicum*), sorghum (*Mediasia macrophylla*),

shungula (*Muretia fragrantisissima*), dill (*Anethum graveolens*), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*).

Fennel - *Pimpinella anisum* fruit contains essential oil, and preparations made from it have anti-inflammatory, expectorant, anti-spasmodic and partially anti-microbial properties. Ibn Sina recommended the use of fennel fruit to relieve breathing difficulties and as an antiperspirant and in other diseases. In folk medicine, a tincture made from the fruit of the plant is used as a diaphoretic, diuretic, diuretic, and appetite suppressant.

Common fennel (fennel) - *Foeniculum vulgare* is a perennial herb (grown biennial in plantations), 90-200 cm tall. The stem is upright, multi-faceted and multi-branched.

The leaf is separated three-four times like feathers and is located in a row on the stem with the sheath. Leaf pieces are thin linear or stringy. The flowers are small, yellow, gathered in a complex umbrella. There will be no leaves in the umbrella. Sepal leaf is very small, 5 sepals, 5 sepals, two-digit maternal node, located below. The fruit is a double pistachio.

The fruit contains essential oil, fat and proteins. Essential oil contains anetal, phenone ketone, methylhavicol, a small amount of anis aldehyde and anis acid, pinene, phellandrene, camphene and other compounds. The fruits and preparations of dill are used as expectorants, laxatives and carminatives for inflammation of the upper respiratory tract, for gastrointestinal diseases and flatulence (intestinal gas accumulation, flatulence). . Sometimes the fruit is also used for gall bladder and kidney stones. Essential oil is used in pharmaceuticals to improve the taste of mixtures.

Planted coriander - *Coriandrum sativum* is an annual herb growing 30-70 cm tall. The stem is cylindrical, fine-edged, hairless, hollow inside, branched at the top. The leaves are simple, scabbard, hairless, the basal leaves are long-banded, cut into three parts, the edge is cut like a tooth, the leaves in the lower

part of the stem are short-banded, cut into two parts, and those in the middle part are not banded, and the cord is two-three. 'varnish separated. The leaves are arranged in a row on the stem. The flowers are small, collected in a complex umbrella without a general package; calyx five-toothed, preserved with the fruit. Five corollas, pink in color, 5 paternal nodes, two digits of the maternal node, located below. The fruit is round, brown or yellowish-gray, double grain. It is grown in the republics of Central Asia.

Coriander fruit contains essential oil, fat, protein and other substances. The oil contains nalool, geraniol and a small amount of borneol, various aldehydes and mixtures of terpenes.

Coriander fruit is used as an appetite suppressant, digestive aid, expectorant, and in the treatment of hemorrhoids and wounds. Coriander essential oil is used as an antiseptic, pain reliever, expectorant and anti-inflammatory drug, and is also used in pharmaceuticals to improve the taste of drugs. Coriander fruit and essential oil are used in food industry and perfumery.

The tribe unites 8 families. It includes trees, shrubs and grasses. The leaves are mostly opposite. The flowers are different. Flowers are usually bisexual, actinomorphic or zygomorphic

1. *Carum carvi*

2. *Daucus carota*

3. *Ferula foetida*

The family includes about 300 species belonging to 13 families. It is distributed in temperate and cold regions of the Northern Hemisphere. 25 species belonging to two categories grow in Uzbekistan. The leaves are entire, opposite. The calyx is short tubular, the corolla is brown or tubular. The fruit is mainly a berry.

Three (Shilvi) - species of Lonicera family with deciduous, sometimes slightly green and green, branched shrub, sometimes tree, liana. The leaves are simple, sideless, opposite. Flowers are bisexual actinomorphic or zygomorphic. It includes more than 250 species. About 30 species grow in the flora of the CIS. 5 out of 15 species in our republic are planted as ornamental plants around avenues and streets. Pennywort - *L. nummularifolia* is a small branched tree or shrub. It is distributed in mountain groves, bushes and slopes. *L. microphylla* is planted as an ornamental plant in avenues. There are also alkaloid-preserving types of licorice.

Valerian family – Valerianaceae Mostly herbs, sometimes semi-shrubs and shrubs. The leaves are opposite. Usually feathered and without sides. Inflorescences are dikhazi or gajak. Flowers are bisexual, sometimes unisexual, zygomorphic, asymmetric. About 400 species belonging to 13 families are distributed in Eurasia, Brazil and the Andes. In Uzbekistan, 18 species of the family, which belong to 3 categories, grow.

Valeriana is a group of herbs with a thickened root, containing more than 200 thin species, of which 3 species (*V. ficarifolia*, *V. chionophila*, *V. fedtschenkovi*) are distributed in Uzbekistan. Medicinal valerian - *V. officinales* is a large, perennial herb with rhizomes of great importance in medicine. It is not found in the flora of Central Asia.

It grows and is cultivated naturally in Ukraine, Belarus and Russia. The rhizome of the plant is mainly used. Medicines prepared from it are widely used for nervous diseases, heart disease, insomnia. The leaves of some species are used instead of salad.

Dipsacaceae family According to the life form, the family consists of light-loving annual and perennial grasses. The leaves are opposite. Flowers are bisexual, zygomorphic. The flower is tubular. The fruit is a nut.

This family unites about 300 species belonging to 10 families. They are mainly distributed around Eurasia, Africa, Western Asia and the Mediterranean Sea. 11 species belonging to 4 categories grow in Uzbekistan.

Tongiztarak is a biennial, sometimes perennial herb of the Dipsacus family, whose stems and inflorescences are prickly, the flowers are conical, and the stem is branched. The leaves on the stem are opposite, sometimes they are joined at the base. 2 out of 15 species spread on earth grow in our Republic. *D. laciniatus* is more than 2 meters tall. The stem is straight-edged, branched on three sides. The flowers are pale poppy or flowing. Biennial grass. It grows as a weed in forests, gardens, wastelands, along roads. Azure sedge - *D. azureus* stem is smooth, the head is elongated, spherical, the flowers are bluish-purple in color, the height is 50-150 cm. It is distributed on the wetter slopes of the mountains. An alkaloid similar to gentianine alkaloid was found in the root.

Scabiosa - species of the Scabiosa family, the head is spherical or egg-shaped, the flowers are red, purple, white, yellow, pink, 5-lobed, the leaves are not turned into thorns. There are about 100 species distributed mainly in the flora of the Mediterranean Sea. Of these, 7 species are distributed in our Republic. Such species as *S. songarica*, *S. oliveri*, and *S. rhodontha* are annual grasses and are widely distributed on hills and foothills with sandy and loamy soil. Most species of the family are cultivated as ornamental plants.

LIST OF USED REFERENCES

1. Prator O., Shamsuvaliyeva I., Sulaymonov E., Axunov X., Ibodov K., Mahmudov V. Botanika . Darslik. Toshkent “Таълим нашриёти” 2010, 285 bet.

2. Pratov O`., Nabyev M. O`zbekiston yuksak o`simliklarining zamonaviy tizimi. Toshkent “O`qituvchi”, 2007. 62 bet.

3. Жизнь растений I-VI том. Москва, 1974-1982.

4. Czerepanov S.K. Vascular plants of Russia adjacent states (the former USSR) Cambridge University press, 1995. 516 p.

5. Takhtajan A. Flowering Plants. New York, 2009. 381 p.

6. Тадтаджян А. Система магнолиофитов. Ленинград, Изд. “Наука”, 1987. 439 с.

Пратов У., Тажетдинова Д. “Определитель растений Средний Азии” нинг I-X томларида келтирилган ўсимлик оилалари, туркумларининг лотинча, русча, ва маҳаллий номлари (қўлланма). Тошкент, 2010. 35 бет